
**TEACHING, RESEARCH AND EXTENSION: AN EXPERIENCE
REPORT ON A VISIT TO THE CENTRAL LABORATORY OF FOREST
PRODUCTS AT UFSB**

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AT05: Educação Inclusiva na Educação Básica

Introduction: University outreach activities play a fundamental role in the education of professional citizens and in the democratization of knowledge, promoting a connection between the academic context and social reality. In this sense, the outreach project “Getting to Know Our UFSB” was developed, with the main objective of welcoming high school and elementary school students from the cities of Itabuna and Ilhéus, in southern Bahia, for guided tours of the Federal University of Southern Bahia (UFSB). During these visits, students had the opportunity to see the laboratories and the research carried out, with emphasis on the Central Laboratory of Forest Products. The initiative sought not only to present the structure and opportunities offered by the university, but also to awaken the interest of young people in higher education. Through this project, the commitment to social inclusion and the dissemination of knowledge was reinforced, bringing academia closer to society. **Objective:** This study aims to report the experience of students, monitors and lecturers involved in the outreach project “Getting to Know Our UFSB”, highlighting the impacts and learning generated by the initiative. **Experience Report:** The visits took place from October 3, 2023 to October 19, 2023. To welcome the visiting students, a monitor and a lecturer were selected to represent each laboratory involved. At the Central Forest Products Laboratory, those responsible addressed topics related to wood science and technology. To this end, dynamic presentations were prepared that included the handling of microscopes and magnifying glasses, in addition to the display of histological slides with anatomical sections of native Brazilian woods. These activities allowed visitors to observe the internal structures of the wood and understand its

functionalities. Based on anatomy, it was possible to discuss the potential uses and utilities of woods, as well as methods to identify and classify forest species. The experience left the students amazed, as they were able to experience the routine of a laboratory at a public university. **Conclusion:** The activity provided mutual benefits to all involved. The lecturers and monitors had the opportunity to experience a socio-educational immersion, exercising and improving their public speaking and communication skills. The visiting students experienced significant educational inclusion, getting to know the university routine and the pleasures of academic life up close. This exchange of knowledge and experiences reinforces the importance of extension projects as tools for democratizing access to knowledge and for building a more just and participatory society.

Keywords: Democratization of knowledge; Socio-educational inclusion; University.